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INFLUENCE AND EXISTENTIALISM IN MODERN INDIAN ENGLISH POETRY: EXPATIATE OF POSTCOLONIAL READING IN SELECTED POEMS OF KAMALA DAS, K.N. DARUWALLA, R. PARTHASARATHY AND A.K. RAMANUJAN

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Abstract:

Indian English poetry often betrays an ‘anxiety’ – on the one hand, it cannot escape contemporary demands of culture; on the other it is unable to forget its colonial past and the inheritance of the language of the rulers. R. Parthasarathy’s poetic venture into English confirms this socio-cultural dilemma. His poetry strives for native roots and attempts to reconnect the fractured bonding of the poet with Tamil culture. His Rough Passage shows in three distinct stages the poet’s traumatic experience in an alien land: initially the poet speaker is in painful banishment; then love and human relationships are shown to be providing some solace; finally the celebration of returning home brings about a harmonious fusion of the Tamil culture and the English language. The growth and development of Indian poetry in English is a result of many experimentations and struggles for a tradition, imitation and innovation with imitation. Right from its beginning, almost all Indian poets of English are found to be continuing these two strains, foreign influences (mainly British) and Indian elements in their poetry. Whether the pre-independent Indian English poetry imitated only the British literature, the post-independent Indian English poetry has imitated world literatures. Indian English poetry, as a post-colonial genre, certainly marks a departure from the traditional notions of poetry and introduces some new ideals. The present paper is an investigation of the growth of the genre vis-à-vis alien influences and individuality which are reconciled in the genre in reciprocal internal commerce.

Introductory Note

K. R. S. Iyengar observes regarding Indian English poetry: “No true poet can escape tradition, for all our yesterdays are involved in the poet’s deeper consciousness; and no true poet can escape the pressure of the present, for he is in it and of it . . .” (Iyengar 641- 2). Indian English poetry has always displayed this kind of ‘anxiety’ – on the one hand, it cannot forget its colonial past and the legacy of the intellectual language of the rulers; on the other hand, even while indulging in self-expression through a foreign language it fails to completely transcend its rootedness or inheritance of the cultural value of its motherland. The result is that Indian mythic tradition is fused with the rationalistic and realistic explorations of the Western movements. The Indian intellectuals were markedly influenced by the streams of British literature but at the same time they acquired their sustaining force from the regional and Sanskrit literature, mainly from the *Vedas*, the *Upanishads*, and from the two great epics the *Ramayana*, and the *Mahabharata*. Primarily the Indian writers, writing in English somewhat imitated the great British Romantic poets, but they were also able to

incorporate the ancient Indian sensibility with their creation. Sometimes they were not given creative status and were merely dismissed as 'a bogie attached to the British engine'. However, we cannot miss the bi-cultural awareness in their writings; they expressed their rich cultural heritage through a foreign language which V. K. Gokak described as 'Shakuntala in a skirt' (ibid.). In the 'New' (Iyengar's term) school of Indian English poets 'the dilemma of belonging to two cultures' is more prominent: for they, well read in Marx, Freud, Pound, Joyce, Eliot looked around themselves and accordingly attempted to express Indian life, its ethos, beliefs, philosophy and landscape. Their poetry is marked by a deliberate 'Indianness' – be it socio-cultural, political or religious and spiritual.

The growth and development of Indian poetry in English is a result of many experimentations and struggles for a tradition, imitation and innovation with imitation. Its growth has never been "sporadic but organismic, along the lines of the British tradition initially, and the tradition of the vernaculars of late" (Amga 1). It has a long history of more than one hundred and fifty years, although there was never a historical past of poetry in Indian writing in English. The term usable past that we generally use in the specific context of a writer's debt to his past here becomes anomalous or redundant. We also find, in many national literatures, that poetry is the root of all literary activities following which all developments have come into existence today, in Indian writing in English, poetry had not provided that source of background from which all other branches of literatures could have emerged. In this sense, when the main body of literature does not have a specific historical background or beginning, then the sense of rootlessness and a derivative and an imitative beginning of a particular genre of that body of literature, i.e., poetry should not be a question of strangeness or critical argument. As we know, a fellow poet always defensively misreads his precursor(s) and distorts him/them beyond recognition in such a way that the belated poet at once creates individuality, then what would be the choice of the Indian English poets in that specific context? Who would be their models? In fact they have had to create their own tradition and individuality by rooting themselves into the European models or in the vernacular literatures.

Right from its beginning almost all the poets of Indian Writing in English are found to be continuing these two strains, i.e., foreign influences (mainly British) and Indian elements in their poetry. The modern Indian English poets "perambulated between the English Romanticism on the one hand and the mythic, folk traditions of the indigenous culture on the other and, in consequence, seemed to have lost their moorings" (ibid). As we know Indian English poetry made its appearance under adverse circumstances when the British ruled supreme over India and Romanticism in their literature, all the pre-independent poets wrote their poetry under the influence of British Romantic poetry. Basically they imitated the technical variations and the vague sentimentality of English Romantic poetry. What they did was a simple political reconciliation of technical mimicry and thematic originality. All these pioneers wrote poetry mainly on Indian myths, religions, ritual elements, national heroes, and on different social problems by imitating technical skills of British poets. They used the resources of British poetry and created a vast body of poetry with its peculiar resonance of meaning and expression aided by the epic and the mythic immensities of the Indian tradition. When a new panorama emerged in Indian English poetry after the independence, poets began to endow with new taste and temperaments, new skills and gestures. Like modern poetry in English literature, most of the pre-independent Indian English poets have attempted to capture the true picture of day-to-day reality, moral and spiritual upheaval corroding the vitals of rich tradition and cultures, a sense of alienation, frustration and desolation in the fragmented society. Almost all the poets of this period come up with their decolonized approaches and individuality to create an indigenous poetic tradition. But that individuality relied, in many cases, on the autobiographical account and the Indianization of the British English. Whether the pre-independent Indian English poetry imitated only the British literature, the post-independent Indian English poetry has imitated world literatures. As Bruce King remarks:

“If at first modern Indian English verse appeared to be indebted to British and a few European models, it now reveals an awareness of most of world literature, including contemporary American, recent South American, and older devotional verse in the regional languages” (5).

Along with Dom Moraes, Siv Kumar, P. Lal, Eunice de Suza, Arun Kolatkar, Jayanta Mahapatra, the four representatives incorporated in this paper- Kamala Das, K.N. Daruwalla, R. Parthasarathy and A.K. Ramanujan are found to be devotees of the same tradition. Kamala Das has close affinity with the Australian poet Judith Right and the American poet Walt Whitman. Jayanta Mahapatra, Kolatkar, Parthasarathy, Ramanujan and even Dom Moraes showed their affinity with the British and American modernists. In their less formal language skills and dictions and the use of highly personal voices to write about ordinary experiences, they reveal their close affinity with modern American poetry. Likewise their responses towards own experiences and “social reality” are almost akin to Eliot, Pound and the other modernists like Hopkins, Auden, the French experimentalists like Rimbaud and Lautreamont to the twentieth century Dadaists and Surrealists. All these poets, on the other hand, show their similarity with the Modernists by going back to myth and past to re-create the lost order and stability of the society. Parthasarathy’s *Rough Passage* (1976), Kolatkar’s *Jejuri* (1976), Mahapatra’s *Close The Sky, Ten By Ten* (1971), *Relationship* (1981) or Daruwalla’s *Under Orion* (1970) and *The Keeper of The Dead* (1982) are some of the well-known examples of this legacy. In their approaches, we find the distance between the modern skeptical individual and the traditional beliefs of the society.

Kamala Das appeared during that transitional period when Indian English poetry marked a departure from colonial and nationalist themes as the re-writing of legends, praise of peasants and from general ethical statements to ‘writing-the-self’ tactics and personal experiences. She belonged to that period of Indian English poetry when initially poetry found expression through technical innovation and thematic newness. As part of the confessional tradition, whereas Ezekiel often made the use of allusion to his life and a desire for personal changes, Kamala Das seems to be confessional through her highly emotive, self-revelatory and moody poems. Whereas, Sarojini Naidu in her love lyrics is more sentimental and devotional, in her personal revelation, Kamala Das treats love within a broader range of themes, more realized settings bringing to it an intensity of emotion and speech and a rich, full complexity of life.

Poetry for Das is a medium of expression of her personal experiences, guilt and inner desires. She writes primarily of her marriage life, love, desire for intimacy, sense of guilt and of her protean self. It is the sentiment that she possesses, makes her poems Indian. Unlike Sarojini, who idealizes her romantic sentiment, Kamala always emphasizes on a picture of personal and family life:

There is an hour now far away where once
I received love. That woman died,
The house withdraws into silence, snakes moved
Among books I was then too young
To read, and, my blood turned cold like the moon.

(The Grandmother’s House)

Throughout her poetic career, suffering was going to be the raw material, if not her poetic inspiration. Her protean creative self is capable of speaking in million different voices. As she says-

I am a million million people

Talking all at once, with voices raised in clamour.

(Someone Else's Song)

However, Das's reconciliation of the first person singular pronoun with the myriad poetic personae clearly shows the American poetic influence on Indian English poetry. In her democratic feelings, here she echoes Walt Whitman's "Song of Myself", where the American poet engulfs the entire mankind in himself:

I am the mate and companion of people all just as

Immortal and fathomless as myself.

(Song of Myself)

It is the American poetic influence which made Indian English poetry less formal and encouraged poets to use highly personal voice and diction to write about ordinary experiences. This strategy in a broader perspective can also be seen as poets' decolonization of British English to create agency towards authenticity and a kind of counter discourse.

However, like other modernists of her time, poetry for Kamala Das is not an escape from personality. For the sake of gender politics, as a female poet, she does not like to escape from herself. It is the self-celebration through which she asserts her female identity and a counter-colonial discourse in her poetry:

Why not let me speak in

Any language I like? The language I speak

Becomes mine, its distortions, its queernesses

All mine, mine alone.

(An Introduction)

In her revelation of fairly personal voice, she is identical with Sylvia Plath, Anne Sexton, Denise Levertov and the Australian poet Judith Write. As a post-colonial poetess, thus, she hardly can go away from western grand narratives, which, up to the emergence of post-structuralism, remain as the deterministic force of various philosophical ideals. In her ambivalent attitude towards sex, she, on the one hand, represents the dilemma of modern Indian women, but, in her feminist outlook she, on the other hand, deals with the universal question of "otherness". She herself recognizes post-colonialism, like feminism, as a theory of engagement- creating agency for the marginalized and the oppressed.

As a contemporary of Kamala Das, Keki N. Daruwalla's place in modern Indian English poetry is very well recognized. Like many other poets of the post-independent period, Daruwalla's main significance lies in his continuing involvement with his poetic self to develop the body of his creation, which ultimately shows his personal quest for order and satisfaction in the modern urban world. In his quest, one can easily find his awareness for others, specific situation, local environment and as well as his awareness for the disordered, miserable world. Unlike Kamala Das, Daruwalla hardly inscribes his autobiographical account as raw material; rather, it is his self-perception of the outer reality which operates as the basis of his poetic creations. The persona of his poems, like Mehrotra and Mahapatra, is not an experimentalist, but a victim of the process of urbanization and social changes. As a result of this victimization, the poet often seems to sink into a state of dilemma and shows his nostalgic yearning for the mythological past as an escape from his sufferings and frustrations. In this approach he is almost identical with modern European poets like Eliot, Pound and W.B. Yeats. Throughout his creations, the poet often shifts his

perspective from freedom to control, reality to illusion or illusion to reality and brings the complexity of psychological tension in his creations. If Kamala Das fully involves with reality itself and Ezekiel tends to be more impersonal in realistic depiction, Daruwalla distorts the reality itself and becomes more metaphorical and symbolic like Yeats.

Like Eliot's Prufrock, the poetic personae of Daruwalla's poems show the predicament of modern individual. He lives in a modern wasteland, where he loses all his hopes and fidelity and becomes a patient:

I know of failing strength and fettering feet

I know I am hungry but I cannot eat

For though I am a patient

For Lamb within me has turned urgent.

(Lambing)

He is an alienated, isolated individual utterly sensible towards the difficulties inside the society. In the process of modernization the society has lost its order and stability and becomes fragmented. It is a world of pious horror of violence and hatred like Eliot's "Wasteland" which the poet visualizes every time:

I can smell violence in the air

like the lash of coming rain

mass hatreds drifting grey across the moon...

(Rumination-I)

Same notion of violence and horror of his social vision are projected in his poems comprising animal imageries. In this aspect Daruwalla shows a poignant influence of Ted Hughes's animal poems where the poet uses animals to reveal deep emotional and intellectual strategies of the mind. Like Hughes's "Hawk Roosting", Daruwalla's "Hawk" is the symbolical expression of the raw energy and the elemental force of nature. The affinity between the two can be well obtained-

Daruwalla's "Hawk"-

I saw the wild hawk-king this morning

riding an ascending wind

as he drilled the sky.

... he uses lost

in the momentum of his own gyre,

a frustrated parricide on the kill.

Ted Hughes's "Hawk Roosting"-

It took the whole creation

To produce my foot, my each feather.

Now I hold creation in my foot

...I kill where I please because it is all mine.

This similarity becomes more specific in Daruwalla's "Wolf", where the animal, like Hughes's "Thought Fox", enters in the poet's mind and consciousness like poetic imagination-

Black snout on sulphur body

He nudged his way

Into my consciousness

(Wolf)

Both the poets are not concerned with the ontological description of animals; they rather use animals to bring other significances and deeper meanings.

Furthermore, Daruwalla has an unerring instinct for painting the landscape, the ever-flowing Ganga and the territorial Ghaghra, the mighty green, gray hills and mountains, infected vales and valleys, the countless trees and bamboos mating against the horizon. In his depiction of the rural India, his sentiment is essentially Indian as it transcends the material needs of human being in order to gain a mystic union with the unseen. His avoidance of the urban and industrial modern societies leads him to enter into a state of dilemma when he often confronts with a complex struggle between physical realism and moral awareness. This conflict is the conflict between conscience and a view of life as power. In this struggle, the poet shows his mytho-poetic imagination and his urge to go back to the mythological past in order to recreate the lost order and stability of the society.

Like Daruwalla, Raja Gopal Parthasarathy has also given a new dimension to Indian English poetry. As an Indian writer in English language he felt doubly alienated from the English language as well as from his own culture. Because of his continuous engagement with the English language and his urge for the Tamil culture he can neither belong to the language properly nor to his Tamil culture. As a diaspora his sense of belonging is always shattered by the conflict between past memories and the present social reality. Thus, it becomes a characteristic feature of his poetry that he always deals with this emotional and spiritual dilemma caused by his sense of rootlessness and urge for belongingness. In this process the poet often, beside his assertion of the mental upheaval and frustration, seems to be reconciling the Tamil past and the impotence that he felt in acquiring a foreign language and also shows his increasing interest in long poems as a means of going beyond the fragmented vision and isolation associated with short lyrics.

During his stay in England, Parthasarathy had found that his English was not idiomatic. Britishers had still retained the oriental binaries and imperialistic attitudes towards India and Indians. These binary positions ultimately brought an orient into the position of "other" and create in him the sense of belonging to his/her culture. As the poet says-

There is something to be said for exile:

You learn, roofs are deep. That language

Is a tree, loses colour

Under another sky.

(Under another sky)

Although in some of his earlier and later works, the significance of love, its essences and emotional complexities with the English language still occur as his major themes. But here love is treated in a more realistic manner, if not like that of his early sentimental ways. In these poems the influence of the British English poets are explicitly revealed. The poet refers to this influence as false teeth:

For many years now he has had his teeth

In the English language- false teeth

His earliest poems were rhymed.

Now rhymes are more fashionable in toothpaste ads.

(False Teeth)

As the poet recognized his faults, he started experimentations over his writing to create something authentic.

His masterpiece *Rough Passage* (1977) comprises three distinct parts namely 'Exile', 'Trial' and 'Homecoming', which were written over a period of fifteen years between 1961-1975. All these three sections reveal Parthasarathy's ceaseless experimentations of the English language as well as his predicament as an English language poet. In the journey, he has recognized the fact that the new environment can change the past superficially; past is always potent in the subconscious. His exile i.e. his diasporic identity has deteriorated his self in such a way that the persona of his poem is now alienated from his own culture:

The hourglass of the Tamil mind is replaced by the exact chronometer of Europe

(Exile)

It is this realization of his inability to recover his linguistic roots and his Tamil past, which brings him the realization of the man-woman relationship in the second section namely "Trial". But his love relation could not make him free from his predicament; dissatisfaction of love relation again brought the sense of alienation into his mind:

My past is an unperfected stone.

The flaws show, I polish

The stone sharpen the luster to a point.

(Trial)

His anxieties regarding colonial influence are freeze in his mind like a stone; through the process of appropriation the poet constantly seeks to 'polish' the stone up to the point of its transformation.

In the final section, the poet explores his experience of returning back to his home and tries to revitalize his Tamil past. By remembering the articulations of his mother tongue, he now glorifies his past and like Whitman in "Song of Myself", tries to be in contact with various significant and insignificant homely activities. The complete journey in the *Rough Passage* shows the poet's resistance and internalization of the colonial legacy and also his gradual development towards construction of a native self. Like Eliot, he believes that a writer is a product of his own culture Ramanujan, Like Parthasarathy, too, asserts the assimilation of two distinct cultures in his writing:

"English and my disciplines...give me my outer forms- linguistic, metrical, logical and other ways of shaping experience, and my fist thirty years in India, my frequent

visits and fieldtrips, my personal and professional preoccupations with Kannada and Tamil, the classic and folklore give me my substance, my “inner” forms, images and symbols...” (96).

This union of the outer and inner forms constitutes the embryo of his poetic genius. His poetry blends the techniques and conventions of European, Indian, American, and British literatures, with those of Kannada, Tamil, and Sanskrit. The identity which is revealed through his poems is not thoroughly an Indian one; he is a postcolonial mimic man- a product of postcolonial “Hybridity”, who, instead of revealing a unique Indian self, always tries to show his anxiety, power of memory, past, and the psychological effect of colonialism. As it can be seen from poems like ‘Conventions of Despair’, ‘Snakes’, ‘Entries for a Catalogue of Fears’, ‘Anxiety’ and ‘Self-Portrait’, he carries his past with him like an inner world of memories and law which erupt into the present, transformed into anxieties, fears and new insights.

It is true to say that Ramanujan mainly follows the metaphysical and the imagist traditions of poetry. Structurally most of the poems in *The Striders* are akin to the metaphysical tradition. On the other hand, the title poem of the volume appears to be a poem in the tradition of the imagists and particularly William Carlos Williams’, in which precise objective description has a philosophical significance. The volume brings direct allusion to Henry David Thoreau’s *Walden*. In his next volume titled *Second Sight* (1986), Ramanujan speaks of myriad poetic selves which a poet possesses during his encounter with the dynamic context of reality.

However, it is remarkable that his ancestry and culture constitute the embryo of his poetry. In his *Relations*, the poet manifesting his re-rooting tendency remarks that without his ancestry he cannot have any identity. Throughout the volume, we can find many references to his Tamil culture and his forefathers, where the poet re-roots himself to make his sense of identity. But this conception regarding self and identity was not evident in his last poems. Towards the end of his career, the poet recognized that the social context was dynamic and every time an individual has to encounter new situations and reality. In this dynamic context human identity does not remain as static. Like Dom Moraes, he constituted the view that art should not be confined within geographical territories and national sentiment. His poetry in this period incorporates assimilates linguistic, literary, and cultural forms of modern American, British, and European literature. Indian sources and influences produce a poetry which has many of its psychological roots in Indian cultural traditions but which have been westernized, modernized, and internationalized.

Conclusion

A brief discussion of these representatives shows that the post-independent Indian English poetry is the conglomeration of foreign and indigenous elements. It is a type of poetry that does not belong to anywhere. The hybrid thematic and technical skills, geographic displacement of poets, socio-cultural assimilations, internalization of colonial influence and the direct influence of the reading of foreign literatures make this poetry homeless and at the same time more fertile. Myths or legends alone cannot constitute the desired Indianness of this genre. During modernism, myths are treated as universal documents of recreating order and stability in society- as we find, Eliot, being an American, concludes his masterpiece *The Waste Land* (1920) with an often quoted allusion to the Indian Upanishads. It is the oriental bias and the urge for belongingness that propel these poets to re-root themselves into their own traditions and cultures. It is this strategic dimension that inclines Indian English poetry to her home.

However, this strategy is more or less is psychological and primarily deals with a subject position and its dimensions are not explicit in artistic creations, but confined within the poet. New critical or deconstructive readings can change their traditional meanings. Indian English poetry, as a post-colonial genre, certainly marks a departure from the

traditional notions of poetry and introduces some new ideals. It celebrates multiculturalism and global identity. The richness which western critics generally fail to notice in this genre lies in its subtle understanding of universal predicament of global displacement and the interdisciplinary aspects of literature. It is the influence that makes this genre homeless, if not inferior; it is this influence that makes Indian English poetry more diversified and peculiar. If we consider this view that every new literature is the re-writing of old literature, then, certainly, Indian English poetry is richer than British literature.

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